

Cultivating Deeper Interdisciplinary Dialogue: Survey Report

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This report in 30 seconds

The *Cultivating Deeper Interdisciplinary Dialogue* project aims to develop a potential framework for teacher professional learning in Wales, centred on disciplinary and interdisciplinary teacher-teacher dialogue.

This report shares findings of a survey carried out in the first half of 2025.

The key findings in this report are based on responses from 291 teachers in secondary schools across Wales.

Teachers in Wales report frequent professional conversations with their teaching colleagues. They are much more likely to talk about the content they are teaching than they are to talk about the purpose of what they are teaching.

The most frequent conversations take place between teachers of the same subject. Conversations about content taught in AoLEs are also frequent, but conversations about content or purpose with teachers outside AoLEs are much less frequent.

Conversations between teachers about the relationship between their subjects are much less frequent than conversations about content or purpose.

Most teachers in the survey agreed that there was a positive school environment to encourage professional dialogue with over 80% agreeing that there was a friendly atmosphere in their school when teachers engaged in curriculum conversations.

there is a collegiate interdisciplinary feel for many teachers. Over 50% reported that senior leaders encouraged curriculum conversations between teachers from different AoLEs and the same number said time was set aside for teachers to support one another on what they teach.

In terms of agency, only 40% of teachers reported that they were given agency to decide the focus of curriculum conversations and, supporting this, over 50% reported that in their school senior leaders decided the focus of curriculum conversations.

Crucially for this project, more than half reported that surface level curriculum conversations for easy solutions were common and only just over 30% reported that deeper, more challenging curriculum conversations were common.

80% of participants suggested that 'subject-specific networks to support professional learning' would support them in deeper curriculum conversations with teachers of other subjects.

In comparison to teacher talk about content, purpose or relationship with other subjects, talk about sustainability and climate change is much less frequent. Over half of survey participants reported never talking to teachers outside their subject about sustainability or climate change issues that they teach.

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Executive Summary

- Teachers in Wales report frequent professional conversations with their teaching colleagues. Of the topics we asked about, the most frequent conversations are about the content that they teach. 70% of teachers in the survey report talking several times a week to colleagues in the same subject about the content they are teaching and a further 18% report such conversations at least once a week. Substantive professional dialogue is flourishing in Welsh schools.
- Teachers in Wales also reported frequent conversations about the content they taught with other teachers in their AoLE. Although only 1 in 10 (9.9%) report such conversations several times a week, a further quarter report having them around once a week (23.6%). So one third of teachers (33.5%) are talking to teachers of different subjects about the content they teach once a week or more.
- Conversations about content with teachers from subjects outside the AoLE do seem to happen, but they appear to be more sporadic. It is worth noting that 15.8% of teachers report never having such conversations about the content they teach with (any) teachers outside their AoLE.
- Teachers' conversations about purpose can be seen as much less common than conversations about content. The most frequent conversations about purpose happen within subject communities of teachers. Over half of teachers report such conversations taking place once a week or more, suggesting teachers are not just talking to their subject colleagues about what they're teaching, they're also talking about why they're teaching such content.
- Conversations about purpose in the AoLE are less frequent, but still significant with over half of teachers reporting them once a month or more. Conversations about purpose outside the AoLE are much less frequent, however. Over 60% of teachers (61.4%) reported that it was once a year or less often (including never) that they have conversations about the purpose of their subject with teachers from other subjects outside their AoLE. This is perhaps not unexpected, but a significant finding which supports the SRE project findings about departments working independently. We need to ask whether the introduction of AoLEs in Wales unintentionally reduces such conversations with subject teachers outside the AoLE.
- Conversations between teachers about the relationship between their subjects are much less frequent than conversations about content or purpose. Still, a significant number of such conversations seem to be taking place in Wales.
- Over 40% of teachers (42.4%) reported such conversations taking place within their subject community one a week or more and a further 40% reported such conversations once a month. This means that within subject communities the relationship between that subject and other subjects is a popular conversation topic among teachers in Wales with over 80% (82.8%) reporting such conversations once a month or more.
- Such conversations, concerning the relationship between the two subjects are slightly less common in the AoLEs with 62% reporting such conversations once a month or more. Again the subject and AoLE groupings dominate the conversations as 17.2% of teachers report never having talking to teachers outside their subject and AoLE about the relationship between the subjects and a further 44.6% report only having those conversations once a year. Only 37.2% reported such conversations as once a month or more.
- Most teachers in the survey agreed that there was a positive school environment to encourage professional dialogue. Nearly 80% of teachers agreed that there was a friendly atmosphere in their

school when teachers in engaged in curriculum conversations and almost 70% agreed that teachers discussed different perspectives when talking about curriculum content.

- And there is a collegiate interdisciplinary feel for many teachers. Over 50% reported that senior leaders encouraged curriculum conversations between teachers from different AoLEs and the same number said time was set aside for teachers to support one another on what they teach.
- Teachers in Wales appear brave with only 30% report avoiding more sensitive issues in their curriculum conversations.
- In terms of agency, however, only 40% of teachers reported that they were given agency to decide the focus of curriculum conversations and, supporting this, over 50% reported that in their school senior leaders decided the focus of curriculum conversations.
- Crucially for this project, more than half reported that surface level curriculum conversations for easy solutions were common and only just over 30% reported that deeper, more challenging curriculum conversations were common.
- Survey participants were given 7 different ideas of what might support them in deeper curriculum conversations with teachers in different subjects. The most popular was more time away from teaching (82.6%). Teachers in Wales clearly feel that their timetable is crowded and that there is little time safeguarded for deep curriculum conversations.
- Shortly behind this though came ‘subject-specific networks to support professional learning’ with 79.7% agreeing with the statement
- In comparison to teacher talk about content, purpose or relationship with other subjects, talk about sustainability and climate change is much less frequent. Talk in the subject area (about what is taught in the subject area related to SCC) still dominates (39.7% report once a month or more).
- Conversations on SCC with teachers of other subjects appeared much less common. Only 17.2% reported having conversations with teachers outside their subject, once a month or more about SCC issues that they taught.
- The ‘never’ data is significant for all the SCC questions. A third of teachers (33.8%) report never talking to teachers in their subject about SCC issues within their subject area (with a further quarter (26.5%) only having these conversations once a year). 43.4% of teachers report never talking to teachers in their subject about SSC issues beyond the subject area and a further 29% report this happening only once a year. There are even starker findings when conversations on SSC issues with teachers of other subjects are considered. Over half (52.2%) report never talking to teachers outside their subject about sustainability or climate change issues that they teach. A further 3 in 10 (30.7%) report this only taking place once a year. So in total, 82.9% of teachers report having a conversation with a teacher in a different subject about SCC issues that they teach once a year or less.
- This may be part of a larger problem as 48.2% of participants report never talking to teachers outside their subject, in their school, about sustainability or climate issues in general with a further 32.8% reporting such conversations taking place only once a year. This is a total of 81% of teachers surveyed in Wales reporting very rare conversations about sustainability and climate change with teachers of other subjects. This raises significant questions about the dialogic opportunities that need to be created before teachers could effectively plan for cross-subject teaching in this area.

Introduction

The *Cultivating Deeper Interdisciplinary Dialogue* project aims to develop a potential framework for teacher professional learning in Wales, centred on disciplinary and interdisciplinary teacher-teacher dialogue. Despite the encouragement for disciplinary and interdisciplinary learning through the recent innovations of *Curriculum for Wales*, we were concerned that interdisciplinary collaboration would run the risk of being shallow if teachers were not given the time, space and opportunity to have conversations about the content and purpose of their different subjects (<https://hwb.gov.wales/curriculum-for-wales/curriculum-for-wales-the-journey-to-curriculum-roll-out/> Accessed 19 December 2025)

The first step of this project was to set up a ‘spotlight’ survey to explore teachers’ current experiences of disciplinary and interdisciplinary dialogue in Wales, responding to the research question, *What experience do teachers in Wales have of substantive disciplinary and interdisciplinary teacher-teacher dialogue?* We wanted to get a broad picture of the nature and frequency of teachers’ conversations about their subject, both with other teachers of the same subject, teachers in the same Area of Learning and Experience and teachers of subjects beyond their particular Area of Learning and Experience.

Survey design and dissemination

The initial online survey, launched in January 2025, had 5 parts.

Part 1: Informed consent and demographics

Part 2: Frequency of Curriculum Conversations

Part 3: The School Environment and Quality of Dialogue, building on the work of Admiraal and Lockhorst (2012) and Boyd and Glazier (2017)

Part 4: Opportunities for Deepening Interdisciplinary Dialogue, building on work of Greer et al. (2023)

Part 5: Talking about Sustainability and Climate Change Education

As uptake was very slow, a second version of the online survey was launched in April 2025 with fewer questions in each section. A third and final version of the survey was launched in June 2025 that was on paper and focused on key questions from Part 1 and Part 5. Each version was translated into Welsh. The online surveys were put on Qualtrics and disseminated to teacher networks through Cardiff Metropolitan University. Social media and teacher educator networks were used to broaden the reach, but it was very difficult to convince teachers to complete the survey. We employed ministry to come up with some new graphics for the project and help with the marketing of the survey.¹

From April to June we shared the survey again using email contacts, social media, ITE networks and networks of RVE teachers and advisers throughout Wales. We approached WJEC exam officers in each subject and asked them to advertise the survey in their newsletters. We also developed a relationship with individuals from Welsh Government and discussed sending out the survey through their email channels, but decided against this as a government badge would not necessarily have encouraged teachers to complete the survey. We sent delegates to RVE conferences and CardiffMet used other meetings of teachers. By June we had 130 teachers engaged with the survey. At this point we decided a new strategy was necessary and a final, short version of the survey which would fit on two sides of one piece of A4 paper was created and translated. We found a small number of willing schools in Wales and promised book vouchers to the school for each completed survey. In this way the number of people engaging with the survey moved to over 300. A

parallel survey was launched in England in an attempt to boost numbers, but responses were low and comparison was tricky due to the lack of an 'AoLE' concept in England.

While over 400 secondary teachers had engaged with one of the three surveys (English in Wales, Welsh in Wales, English in England), several of these had only completed a limited number of questions. It was decided to omit any that were less than 40% complete. The findings shared in the remaining part of this report are based on 331 valid participants across the three surveys. 209 of these came from paper surveys and 122 from the longer online surveys (112 in English and 10 in Welsh). 40 of the online surveys were completions of the 'English in England' survey. 291 of these final analysed surveys were in Wales.

There was a broader set of demographic questions on the online survey. Headlines from these 82 surveys include the following:

- 72 completed in English and 10 in Welsh
- 18 were from 11-16 schools, 60 from 11-18 schools, 4 from 3-16 schools
- 9 were from Welsh-medium schools, 1 from a sixth form college, 4 from schools for pupils with ALN, none from independent schools, 2 from Catholic schools and 1 from another faith school
- 19 of the teachers reported their school having 1201-1500 students and 5 reported being from schools with 1501-1800 students. The others were spread across a range of responses.
- These 82 responses came from 13 different Local Authorities. Cardiff had the highest number with 13, followed by Caerphilly with 12 and Newport with 10.
- 28 of these 82 participants described themselves as teacher, with 43 middle leader (curriculum), 4 middle leader (pastoral), 8 senior leader and 1 headteacher.
- Responses in this set of 82 came from a wide variety of subject teachers, with 11 music teachers, 10 English teachers, 9 Geography teachers, 7 RVE teachers and 7 science teachers.

Reward: In the online survey we offered a financial incentive saying we would donate money to a charity related to Wales based on the number of responses. 9 chose sizeofwales.org.uk, 17 chose sustainablewales.org.uk and 28 chose Friends of the Earth Cymru.

For the survey that was also completed on paper we have the following demographic headlines: 15 subjects were represented in the Welsh survey with 28 teachers of English, 14 of Welsh, 13 of International languages, 27 of Maths, 32 of science and 28 of RVE. 27 chose 'other'.

Findings Part 1: Frequency of conversations

Conversations about content

We asked teachers how often they talked to teachers in their main subject, in their school, about the content of their subject. Options for response ranged from ‘never’ to ‘several times a week.’ Figure 1 shows responses for online and paper surveys in Wales.

Figure 1: Frequency of conversations about content in subject, AoLE and beyond AoLE

The most frequent conversations reported on curriculum content are between teachers of the same subject. In blue we can see nearly 7 in 10 (69.3%) teachers reported such conversations taking place several times a week with a further 2 in 10 (17.8%) reporting conversations about content with teachers of the same subject around once a week. This suggests teachers are talking frequently about what they teach, usually to other teachers who teach the same subject.

Teachers in Wales also reported frequent conversations about the content they taught with other teachers in their Area of Learning and Experience (AoLE). Although only 1 in 10 (9.9%) report such conversations several times a week, a further quarter report having them around once a week (23.6%). So one third of teachers (33.5%) are talking to teachers of different, but related, subjects about the content they teach once a week or more. A further third (33.5%) report having such conversations ‘around once a month’.

There is a different pattern for conversations with teachers outside the subject area and outside the AoLE. Here a much smaller number (14.1%) of teachers report having conversations about the content they teach once a week or more, although a further third (32.4%) report them once a month and a further third again (36.6%) report having them once a year. Conversations about content with teachers

from subjects outside the AoLE do seem to happen, but they appear to be more sporadic. It is worth noting that 15.8% of teachers report never having such conversations about the content they teach with teachers outside their AoLE. This shows us that teachers’ conversations about content in Wales are much more frequent within subject communities.

Conversations about purpose

The second question in this part of the survey asked teachers how often they talked to teachers in the three levels about the purpose of the subject they teach. Figure 2 shows responses for online and paper surveys in Wales.

Figure 2: Frequency of conversations about purpose in subject, AoLE and beyond AoLE

When the data in Figure 2 is compared to Figure 1, teachers’ conversations about purpose can be seen as much less common than conversations about content, across every level. There is a similar pattern in that the most frequent conversations about purpose (31.2% report several times a week) happen within subject communities of teachers. Over half of teachers (57.2%) report such conversations taking place once a week or more and over 80% of teachers (81.4%) report such conversations happening once a month or more often. This suggests teachers are not just talking to their subject colleagues about what they’re teaching, they’re also talking about why they’re teaching such content, just less frequently than talking about the content itself.

Conversations about purpose in the AoLE are less frequent, but still significant, considering that this involves teachers talking to teachers of another subject about why they teach what they teach. A quarter of teachers (24.9%) report such conversations once a week or more and over half (56.5%) report such conversations once a month or more. One in eight (12.3%) teachers report that they never have such conversations. This is interesting as it reports teachers talking to teachers of other subjects about

the purpose of what they are trying to achieve in their curriculum subject. We might expect these conversations to be less frequent in a country which doesn't have the AoLE framework for grouping subjects.

Conversations reported outside the AoLE about purpose are much less frequent than those in the AoLE or in the subject community. Fewer than 1 in 10 teachers (8.4%) report weekly conversations about the purpose of their subject with teachers outside their AoLE. Nearly a quarter (23.9%) report never having such conversations. Over 60% of teachers (61.4%) reported that it was once a year or less often (including never) that they have conversations about the purpose of their subject with teachers from other subjects outside their AoLE. This is perhaps not unexpected, but a significant finding which supports the SRE project findings in England about departments working independently and teachers holding misconceptions about the purpose of other subjects (Woolley et al., 2023; Woolley et al., 2024). It is important to ask whether the introduction of AoLEs in Wales, while perhaps increasing conversations within the AoLE, unintentionally reduces such conversations with subject teachers outside the AoLE.

Conversations about the relationship between subjects

While the initial survey asked about conversations on different topics such as approaches to teaching and or research and scholarship, in the shortened survey we wanted to choose 3 key conversation topics. As we're interested in interdisciplinary conversations, we chose to ask teachers how often they talked about the relationship between subjects in school, whether within their own subject community or beyond. Figure 3 shows the frequency of teachers' reported conversations about the relationship between subjects, in blue at subject level, in orange at AoLE level and in green beyond the AoLE.

Figure 3: Frequency of conversations about the relationship between subjects in subject, AoLE and beyond AoLE

A comparison between Figures 1, 2 and 3 shows reported conversations between teachers about the relationship between their subjects are much less frequent than conversations about content or purpose. Still, a significant number of such conversations seem to be taking place in Wales.

Over 40% of teachers (42.4%) reported such conversations taking place within their subject community once a week or more and a further 40% reported such conversations once a month. This means that within subject communities the relationship between that subject and other subjects is a conversation topic among teachers in Wales with over 80% (82.8%) reporting such conversations once a month or more. Perhaps due to the language of interdisciplinarity in Curriculum for Wales and the introduction of AoLE groups of subjects, teachers are having conversations about how their own subject relates to other subjects.

These conversations about the relationship between subjects also seem to be taking place within the AoLEs. They are slightly less common than within subject groups, with 62% reporting such conversations once a month or more (in comparison to 82.8% within the subject), but nonetheless, teachers are reporting such conversations.

Conversations about the relationship between the subjects outside the AoLE are much rarer, with a comparative 37% reporting them once a month or more. Again the subject and AoLE groupings dominate the conversations as 17.2% of teachers report never having talking to teachers outside their AoLE about the relationship between their subjects and a further 44.6% report only having those conversations once a year. While these figures may not be surprising, they do raise questions about what teachers can know of the curriculum beyond their AoLE and this has implications for students' experience of a coherent curriculum. In Curriculum for Wales, the principle of subsidiarity might mean that the curriculum in one school is quite different to that in another. How can a teacher of one subject,

new to a school, find how their subject fits within the coherent whole, if their opportunities to talk to teachers of other subjects are limited?

Conversations about content, purpose and relationship by subject taught

The following breakdowns, Figures 4, 5 and 6, repeat analysis of the questions covered in Figures 1, 2 and 3, but this time broken down according to 5 key subjects, decided according to the numbers on participants in the survey.

Figure 4: Talk about content once a week or more by subject taught (For English, n=28, for Maths, n=27, for science, n=32, for RVE, n=28 and for PE, n=34)

Figure 5: Talk about purpose once a week or more by subject taught (For English, n=28, for Maths, n=27, for science, n=32, for RVE, n=28 and for PE, n=34)

Figure 6: Talk about relationship between subjects once a week or more by subject taught (For English, n=28, for Maths, n=27, for science, n=32, for RVE, n=28 and for PE, n=34)

Figures 4, 5, and 6 repeat the patterns seen earlier in that conversations about content across all 5 subjects are more common than conversations about purpose, and conversations about the relationships between subjects tend to trail into third.

There are some discrepancies to this general pattern. RVE has a different pattern, with reported conversations within the subject lower than other subjects across all three graphs. This could be related to smaller departments

in RVE. It is worth noting that fewer conversations within the subject, seem to be made up for by conversations in the AoLE, at least in terms of conversations about content and purpose.

PE stands out in conversations about purpose, with more than 4 out of 5 (81.8%) reporting conversations once a week or more about the purpose of the subject. This might relate to a newly defined subject within Curriculum for Wales, or the higher level of conversation could relate to a subject that is often taught outside the confines of a classroom, where perhaps there are more opportunities for conversation.

In comparison to the other subjects, teachers of English and maths report far fewer conversations outside their subject communities – on these three topics at least.

Humanities subjects: Conversations about content, purpose and relationship by subject taught

Figure 7: Humanities teachers' frequency of conversations about content, purpose and relationships with other subjects (talking once a week or more) History (n=10); Geography (n=19); RVE (n=28)

One AoLE, Humanities, was broken down by subject for responses to these three questions. The numbers of teachers are smaller here, raising questions rather than answering them. For example:

- Why are Geography teachers less likely to have conversations about content in their AoLE than History and RVE teachers. Are there more connections between the latter two?
- History teachers are more likely to report frequent conversations about content, but less likely to report frequent conversations about purpose
- IN comparisons between the three subjects, RVE teachers are the least likely to have a conversation about content with others in their subject, but the most likely to have a conversation about purpose.
- As with the other data reported above, conversations about content, purpose and relationships between subjects can be seen to be rare outside the Humanities AoLE.

Conversations about content, purpose and relationship by AoLE

Figure 8: Comparing frequency of conversations about content across AoLEs

(Humanities, n=58, Health and Wellbeing, n=34, Expressive Arts, n=31, Languages, n=55 and Maths, n=27)

For the following analysis, we wanted to breakdown the frequency of conversation according to AoLE in order to compare across the AoLEs. For Figures 8, 9 and 10, the n for each AoLE is as follows: (Humanities, n=58, Health and Wellbeing, n=34, Expressive Arts, n=31, Languages, n=55 and Maths, n=27)

-Across all 5 AoLEs, talk about content was more frequent in the subject (seen by the purple 'several times a week' bar than in the AoLE or beyond the AoLE

- Science and Technology, as an AoLE, reported the most frequent conversations about content, both within the subject and within the AoLE.

- Humanities seems to have a different pattern to other AoLEs, with less frequent conversations about content than other AoLEs.

- For Maths, the 'Not relevant' option was common as there is no other subject in the AoLE.

Figure 9: Comparing frequency of conversations about purpose across AoLEs

(Humanities, n=58, Health and Wellbeing, n=34, Expressive Arts, n=31, Languages, n=55 and Maths, n=27)

As discussed above, reported conversations about purpose are less frequent than conversations between teachers about the content they teach. In comparing Figure 9 with Figure 8, this can be seen to be true across all the AoLEs.

- In newly defined areas, such as Health and Wellbeing, talk about purpose can be seen to be more frequent than in AoLEs with more traditionally defined subjects such as Maths.
- The above is true at both subject and AoLE level.
- The dark blue on this graph shows where teachers reported 'never' having conversations about purpose. In the third graph here, 'outside my AoLE' this stands out for Maths (over 30%), Expressive Arts (just under 30%), Languages and Humanities (both just over 20%). This raises questions over whether the purpose of some subjects are seen to be more obvious and consistent and therefore less discussed across the school.

Figure 10: Comparing frequency of conversations about relationships between subjects across AoLEs

(Humanities, n=58, Health and Wellbeing, n=34, Expressive Arts, n=31, Languages, n=55 and Maths, n=27)

Talk about relationship with other subjects, in subject

Talk in AoLE about relationship between subjects

Talk about relationship between subjects outside AoLE, by AoLE

Figure 10 focuses on conversations about relationship with other subjects, broken down by AoLE.

In the first graph, the green columns show that when such talk happens, it's generally once a month. Only teachers in the science and technology AoLE report such talk as more frequent.

In the second graph, again, talk about relationship between the subjects, within the AoLE generally happens once a month, apart from in languages and maths where an equal number of teachers report frequency as once a year.

Conversations outside the AoLEs about relationship between subjects seem to happen either once a month or once a year, with a preference for once a year.

A substantial number (over 10%) in each AoLE, and nearly 20% in science and technology, reported never having conversations about the relationship between subjects outside the AoLE.

Part 2: The School Environment and Quality of Dialogue

Part 2 of the survey explored descriptions of the quality of dialogue and factors in the environment that might affect dialogue such as agency and time. A 5-point Likert scale was used to gather data across the 9 questions. As this part of the survey was omitted from the later, paper version, the number of participants is lower, at 82. These 82 teachers, however, come from a wide range of Local Authorities across Wales and teach the full range of secondary subjects.

Figure 11: Factors affecting quality of teacher-teacher dialogue (agree or strongly agree)

The summary of responses in Figure 9 shows the teachers who agreed or strongly agreed with each statement. In terms of the quality of conversation, nearly 80% of teachers agreed that there was a friendly atmosphere in their school when teachers engaged in curriculum conversations and almost 70% agreed that teachers discussed different perspectives when talking about curriculum content. More than half of participants, however, reported that surface level curriculum conversations for easy solutions were common and only just over 30% reported that deeper, more challenging curriculum conversations were common.

In terms of agency, only 40% of teachers reported that they were given agency to decide the focus of curriculum conversations and, supporting this, over 50% reported that in their school senior leaders decided the focus of curriculum conversations. Teachers in Wales appear brave though in what they discuss - only 30% report avoiding more sensitive issues in their curriculum conversations.

These figures suggest that there is a collegiate interdisciplinary feel for many teachers. Over 50% reported that senior leaders encouraged curriculum conversations between teachers from different AoLEs and the same number said time was set aside for teachers to support one another on what they teach. It is worth noting that,

while half of teachers said here that curriculum conversations between teachers from different AoLEs were encouraged by senior leaders, the previous section showed data to suggest such conversations were rare.

Despite the small number of participants for this part of the survey, we delve a little deeper into the data for some of the questions on environment and quality of dialogue. Figures 10, 11 and 12 give some further insights into the school environment and support for curriculum conversations, whereas Figures 13, 14 and 15 focus on the perceived quality of existing dialogue.

Figure 12: Full data set on time set aside for teachers to support one another on what they teach (n=82)

Figure 10 shows inconsistency from teachers across Wales in response to this question. While around half (52%) agree that time is set aside for teachers to support one another on what they teach, nearly a third disagree, suggesting that they don't feel such time is set aside. This could be disagreement over the amount of time teachers are given for such support, or the nature of the support they receive. It would be interesting to follow up this item with questions to teachers on what time is set aside and how they support one another. The earlier findings in this report suggest that many conversations between teachers are about the content taught, but that most of these occur within the subject area.

Figure 11: Full data set on senior leaders deciding the focus of curriculum conversations (n=82)

Figure 11 shows that half (50.7%) of teachers who responded to the online survey felt that senior leaders decided the focus of their curriculum conversations. In the full data set here we can see that nearly a quarter of teachers (24.7%) chose neither agree nor disagree, suggesting that senior leaders sometimes control the focus of their curriculum conversations. Indeed, it is only a quarter (24.6%) that outright disagree that senior leaders control the focus of their curriculum conversations, suggesting that they have agency to decide the focus of curriculum conversations for themselves, as teachers. These findings are supported, to some extent, by Figure 12

Figure 12: Full data set on teachers being given agency to decide the focus of curriculum conversations (n=82)

Figure 12, like Figure 11, reveals almost a third of teachers chose the middle option, possibly due to sometimes being given agency in conversations. It is only a quarter of teachers (26%) that disagreed with the statement, suggesting that they rarely had agency over curriculum conversations, which raises questions about how the two questions fit together. Teachers might feel that other groups, such as middle leaders, control the focus of curriculum conversations.

This project set out to support and cultivate deeper curriculum conversations, particularly interdisciplinary conversations. This survey gave the opportunity for a snapshot of teachers’ perceptions on whether those deeper curriculum conversations are taking place.

Figure 13: Full data set on occurrence of deeper, more challenging curriculum conversations

While only around a third of teachers (31.5%) agreed that deeper, more challenging curriculum conversations were common, 4 in 10 (39.7%) disagreed with the statement, suggesting that deeper, more challenging conversations were not common in more schools. We also asked the alternative question, considering the occurrence of surface-level conversations, with the results shown in Figure 14.

Figure 14: Full data set on occurrence of surface-level curriculum conversations (n=82)

Here, the results are clearer and support the same conclusion, that work needs to be done in many schools in Wales to support teachers to have deeper curriculum conversations. Over half of teachers (53.4%) agreed with the statement on surface level curriculum conversations being common, but only 16.5% directly disagreed with the statement.

Figure 15: Full data set on avoiding more sensitive issues in curriculum conversations

Figure 15 also pertains to the quality of curriculum conversations held by teachers. The large numbers selecting middle options could suggest that this was a tricky question about which to generalise. 3 in 10 teachers still agreed with the proposition that more sensitive issues were avoided in curriculum conversations. The large central number could relate to teachers not seeing the content of their subject on the curriculum as sensitive in any way.

Part 3: Opportunities for Deepening Interdisciplinary Dialogue

In this part of the survey participants were given 7 different ideas to support them in deeper curriculum conversations with teachers in different subjects. There was a 5-point Likert scale for responses. Figure 16 summarises the agree/ strongly agree responses.

Figure 16: Teacher affordances for deeper curriculum conversations

The most popular option was more time away from teaching (82.6%). Teachers in Wales clearly feel that their timetable is crowded and that there is little time safeguarded for deep curriculum conversations. Shortly behind this though came ‘subject-specific networks to support professional learning’ with 79.7% agreeing with the statement. This is explored further in Figure 18 and below. Only a third of teachers (31.9%) responded that they felt ‘deeper subject knowledge of my subject’ would lead to deeper curriculum conversations. We need to know what they expect from subject-specific networks and professional learning if it is not deeper subject knowledge. It may be that teachers, within the newness of Curriculum for Wales, want the support of being around teachers of their own subject and professional networks in order to build confidence to engage effectively with teachers of other subjects.

‘Deeper subject knowledge of other subjects’ was a popular option with over half (53.5%) of participants agreeing that it would deepen their curriculum conversations. ‘A shared sense of purpose’ was more popular with 63.8% of participants agreeing. The modelling of conversations by senior leaders (49.2%) or other teachers (56.5%) were popular with around half of teachers responding to the survey.

As the idea of subject-specific networks to support professional learning was popular, with nearly 80% of teacher respondents agreeing, it is worth a closer look at the full data set.

Figure 17: Full data set for subject-specific networks supporting professional learning to have deeper curriculum conversations (n=82)

Figure 17 shows that only a small number (7.2% disagreed with this statement, emphasising the request of subject-specific networks to support professional learning. It would be interesting to break the data for this question down by subject, but numbers were too small to give meaningful results.

Part 4: Talking about Sustainability and Climate Change Education

When designing this project we wanted to take a topic which is agreed to be transdisciplinary, where teachers knowing what is taught across the curriculum would help them support students to a better understanding of the topic. We chose Sustainability and Climate Change Education. We therefore wanted to include it in the survey, to see what conversations teachers were having with teachers within and beyond their subject about sustainability and climate change, both the areas of the topic they taught and wider general issues.

First we asked about the conversations teachers have with other teachers in their subject, about sustainability and climate change issues within their subject area. In Figure 18, those conversations are represented in dark blue. A third of teachers (33.8%) responded never and a further quarter (26.1%) responded once a year. At the same time, a quarter (26.1%) are having this conversation around once a month and a small number (13.6%) are having conversations about sustainability and climate change in their subject once a week or more.

Figure 18: Talk about sustainability (n=291)

In comparison to Figures 1, 2 and 3 reporting on conversations about content, purpose and relationships with other subjects, we can see that talk about sustainability and climate change is much less frequent. Talk in the subject area about the subject area (but related to SCCE) still dominates (39.7% report once a month or more), when compared to talking to teachers inside the subject about SCC issues beyond the subject area (27.6% report once a month or more).

Represented in green on Figure 18, conversations with teachers of other subjects appeared very rare, even on SCC topics taught. Nearly 1 in 5 (17.2%) reported these taking place once a month or more,

but for the other 4 in 5, they are very rarely having conversations about teaching SCC with teachers in other subjects, if at all. However, it's also notable that any conversations about SCC issues in general (not topics taught necessarily) were also rare with teachers outside the subject (19% reporting once a month or more).

The significant column in this graph is really under 'never'. A third of teachers (33.8%) report never talking to teachers in their subject about SCC issues within their subject area (with a further quarter (26.5%) only having these conversations once a year). 43.4% of teachers report never talking to teachers in their subject about SSC issues beyond the subject area and a further 29% report this happening only once a year.

There are even starker findings when conversations on SSC issues with teachers of other subjects are considered. Over half (52.2%) report never talking to teachers outside their subject about sustainability or climate change issues that they teach. A further 3 in 10 (30.7%) report this only taking place once a year. So in total, 82.9% of teachers report having a conversation with a teacher in a different subject about SCC issues that they teach once a year or less.

This may be part of a larger problem as 48.2% of participants report never talking to teachers outside their subject, in their school, about sustainability or climate issues in general with a further 32.8% reporting such conversations taking place only once a year. This is a total of 81% of teachers surveyed in Wales reporting very rare conversations about sustainability and climate change with teachers of other subjects. This raises significant questions about how cross-subject planning or teaching in this area could take place.

Figure 19: Talk about approaches to teaching sustainability and climate change (n=291)

The previous point is supported by Figure 19. While there are some teachers having conversations about how they approach teaching sustainability and climate change issues, the majority of teachers never or very rarely talk about this. Conversations are more likely to happen within the subject, although the difference is not as stark as in some of the other areas for conversation discussed above.

Breaking down the data, we wanted to explore frequency of conversations about teaching sustainability and climate change in different AoLEs.

Figure 20: Frequency of talk about sustainability and climate change within subject area by AoLE (Humanities, n=58, Health and Wellbeing, n=34, Expressive Arts, n=31, Languages, n=55 and Maths, n=27)

Figure 20 breaks down the large ‘never’ data reported earlier so that we can see Maths teachers report far fewer conversations about sustainability and climate change within their subject area (64% report never, 88% once a year or less). Health and wellbeing and expressive arts are not far behind with 50% reporting never having this conversation within their subject area. Reported conversations are more frequent in the Humanities and Science and Technology AoLEs, fitting with what we know about sustainability and climate change frequently being taught in Geography and Science. Indeed 32% of science and technology teachers and 21% of humanities teachers report having such conversations once a week or more.

Figure 21 Frequency of talk about sustainability and climate change beyond subject area (by AoLE) (Humanities, n=58, Health and Wellbeing, n=34, Expressive Arts, n=31, Languages, n=55 and Maths, n=27)

Figure 21, reporting conversations with teachers of the same subject about sustainability and climate change beyond the subject, has a similar spread of responses. Again, the Humanities AoLE and the Science and Technology AoLE lead the way in frequency of conversations with teachers in their subject about sustainability and climate change issues beyond their subject area. Figure 22 shows it is the same two AoLEs that lead the way in conversations about approaches to teaching sustainability and climate change.

Figure 22: Frequency of teacher talk within subject on approaches to teaching sustainability and climate change (by AoLE) (Humanities, n=58, Health and Wellbeing, n=34, Expressive Arts, n=31, Languages, n=55 and Maths, n=27)

Figure 23: Frequency of teacher talk beyond subject area on approaches to teaching sustainability and climate change (by AoLE) (Humanities, n=58, Health and Wellbeing, n=34, Expressive Arts, n=31, Languages, n=55 and Maths, n=27)

Figure 23, however, suggests that such conversations about approaches to teaching SCC are confined to the subject area, with very small numbers reporting conversations of once a month or more in this area (18% in Humanities and 20% in Science and Technology).

Figure 24: Frequency of talk with teachers outside the subject about sustainability and climate change topics that we teach (by AoLE) (Humanities, n=58, Health and Wellbeing, n=34, Expressive Arts, n=31, Languages, n=55 and Maths, n=27)

As we have an interest in transdisciplinary approaches to teaching sustainability and climate change, and students coherent experience of this topic area, Figure 24 becomes a key graph.

This is a key graph. Even in science and technology, where we know sustainability and climate change are being taught, 38% of teachers report never talking to teachers outside their subject about what they teach in this area and a further 37% report only talking about such things once a year.

Figure 25: Frequency of talk with teachers outside the subject about sustainability and climate change in general (by AoLE) (Humanities, n=58, Health and Wellbeing, n=34, Expressive Arts, n=31, Languages, n=55 and Maths, n=27)

Figure 25 could suggest that those who are teaching some sustainability and climate change are more likely to have general conversations with colleagues about sustainability and climate change, with Science and Technology and Humanities AoLEs least likely to report never having the conversations. One wonders why such conversations are not happening – whether through sensitivity or lack of interest? Indeed, considering this same question broken down by subject in the humanities AoLE (Table 1), we can see that Geography teachers are least likely to report never having such conversations in comparison to History and RVE teachers. When they do talk about sustainability or climate change issues in general with teachers outside their subject though, they report that as just being around once a year.

Humanities and SCC

Table 1: Sustainability talk across Humanities subjects.

I talk to teachers in my subject, in my school about: - sustainability or climate change issues within our subject area.					
	Never (%)	once a year (%)	once a month (%)	once a week (%)	several times a week (%)
History	30	20	30	10	10
Geography	5.3	5.3	57.9	21.1	5.3
RVE	10.7	28.6	35.7	14.3	0
I talk to teachers in my subject, in my school about: - sustainability or climate change issues beyond our subject area.					

	Never	once a year	once a month	once a week	several times a week
History	30	30	30	0	10
Geography	5.3	36.8	42.1	5.3	5.3
RVE	25	25	32.1	7.1	0
I talk to teachers inside my subject, in my school about: - approaches to teaching sustainability and climate change					
	Never	once a year	once a month	once a week	several times a week
History	30	30	30	0	10
Geography	15.8	21.1	42.1	10.5	5.3
RVE	28.6	17.9	35.7	7.1	0
I talk to teachers outside my subject, in my school about: - sustainability or climate change issues in general					
	Never	once a year	once a month	once a week	several times a week
History	40	40	10	0	10
Geography	31.6	42.1	21.1	0	0
RVE	35.7	35.7	21.4	0	0
I talk to teachers outside my subject, in my school about sustainability or climate change issues that we teach					
	Never	once a year	once a month	once a week	Several times a week
History	40	40	10	0	10
Geography	42.1	31.6	21.1	0	0
RVE	46.4	25	21.4	0	0

There are various specific findings hidden in this table, but generally, and probably unsurprisingly, it shows that Geography teachers tend to have more conversations about sustainability and climate change than History and RVE teachers.

Part 5: Qualitative data on teacher-teacher conversations

At the end of the online survey we asked teachers what aspect, or topic, with their subject, if any, best lends itself to the teaching of sustainability and climate change. Some of the interesting comments are included here, sorted by subject.

Geography:

“Loads. Geography is the basis of this. We teach climate change in Year 8 and at GCSE and A level. Sustainability (in many contexts) is central to the subject.”

“Climate Emergency and Nature Emergency, but it comes into everything we do.”

Year 8 Unit, There isn't a Planet B.

RVE

“Environmental ethics”

“Stewardship”

Music:

“Environmental impact of touring musicians. Global and world music. Sustainable instrument creation.”

“Writing music or answering questions on digital platforms rather than using paper.”

“Recycled samba drums”

“song writing or rap”

History

“Industrial Revolution”

Science

“hydrocarbons, eutrophication, extraction of metals.”

“habitats”

English

“non-fiction units such a ‘Our Planet’”

“Persuasive writing e.g. speeches, poetry of climate and environment”

PE

“impact of world games such as Olympics on sustainability, sports facility development.”

This data shows the rich range of topics linked to sustainability and climate change that are taught within secondary schooling in Curriculum for Wales, but the data above suggests that there are few conversations between teachers, linking up the teaching of such topics.

We asked teachers to describe a recent curriculum conversation they had taken part in with the following prompts, What subjects do the others in the conversation teach? Why did the conversation begin? What was the conversation about? What did you decide to do next? Would you like to have more such conversations? 46 teachers gave a response to this question and a selection are represented below.

<p>AOLE meeting, discussing how to evaluate progression steps in order to track progress of students, part of moderation of tracking data.</p>	<p>Discussion about the links between Expressive Arts, Technology and Digital skills about how we can link together and map our curriculums for years 7-9 so that we can show student progression across a range of digital skills. We would like to have substantially more time to discuss this both in this group and with other faculties in the school</p>	<p>History - discussion was around developing assessments which were relevant, useful and authentic. The assessments are under review and likely to change to better fit the CfW formative assessment model and yes, I love these sort of conversations.</p>	<p>Discussion with Head of WB and another teacher of WB. Discussion took place due to new school rules on banning the use of mobile phones and the difficulty in pupils evidencing their practical work (models, drawings etc) in electronic form for submission to WJEC. We have decided to take this back to SLT to find a suitable solution that does not put an onerous amount of work on the teacher.</p>
<p>cross curricular discussions with primary school teachers developing connected progression in the new curriculum. Meeting yearly to discuss developments and progress towards connected progress especially sharing assessment good practice</p>	<p>Discussion about use of Blooms taxonomy in questioning whilst linking it to command questions for exams within the Health and Wellbeing AOLE. Discussed how the Agree, Build and Challenge questioning techniques to facilitate more class discussion and depth of understanding and after researching different questions, identified the cross curricular ones that could be used by staff to strengthen understanding across the AOLE.</p>	<p>I have had discussions with the Welsh teaching about developing models of language and fluency with its application to the teaching of science.</p>	<p>GCSE History specification has been delayed, conversation with a Maths teacher who mentioned interesting reforms to Maths becoming a double award and how this will be graded. I was shocked to hear of other subject reforms that will affect pupils that we don't realise will happen.</p>
<p>Differentiation- All teaching staff were seperated into different groups (mixed areas of learning), and tasked to disscuss our differentiation tactics and what we find works best within our subjects. They wanted us to try other teachers techniques to see how we found they worked within our subjects. I found that staff were not keen or willing to put in the time or effort to this project and that most senior members of staff and staff that have been teaching for 20+ years weren't willing to try new things or accept that a younger 'less experienced' teacher could offer a new and possibly more effective form of differentiation. Due to the resistance of some staff, I found myself not wanting to contribute and ended up sitting on the side-lines.</p>	<p>Discussion on engagement with a colleague for a low ability drama class. Topic: monologues, pupils struggled being independent in rehearsal time so disengaged. Looked at texts to focus on and suggested Blood Brothers. From Mickey's monologue to Mickey's and Edward's duologue. Could look at character analysis, students maybe able to relate to them. After two lessons had a check in conversation and the new supporting text focus has worked. Pupils are far more engaged and behaviour has improved.</p>	<p>I spoke to my Head of Department (English) about curriculum due to looking at the NEA questions released for the new GCSE in our subject. We discussed the questions about power and how to teach/explain about power. It was only a brief conversation. I mentioned I was already developing resources on power for the current Year 9s. I would like to have more of these conversations and opportunities to actually sit down and dedicate time to these rather than them be in snippets.</p>	<p>Geography teachers' discussion about the Bushmeat Decision Making Exercise that Yr 8 are carrying out. This conversation began in our Department Learning Exchange meeting. We wanted to make sure everyone was happy with the different elements and shared tips from what we had already done. We agreed to continue with the DME using the tweaks. I would like to have more of these conversations.</p>

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